

PROGRAMME / PROGRAM

**SOCIETE INTERNATIONALE POUR L'ETUDE
DE LA PHILOSOPHIE MEDIEVALE**

XV^e Congrès International de Philosophie Médiévale
Paris-Aubervilliers, 22-26 août 2022

The XVth International Congress of Medieval Philosophy
Paris-Aubervilliers, 22-26 August 2022

LA PENSEE RADICALE AU MOYEN ÂGE

RADICAL THINKING IN THE MIDDLE AGES

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perfective telos. It is something human beings can reach through their own efforts. But, it is not only something human beings can do, but also something it seems that human beings ought to do. This ethical question, that arises from Albert's ordered scientific program of study, is not a question of the division of the sciences. Albert made a clear three-fold division of the sciences in his *Physica*: the rational sciences (such as logic), the real sciences (mathematics, natural sciences, and metaphysics), and the practical sciences (ethics and politics). It is rather a question of relationship, a relationship which Albert made more evident throughout his commentary project. For instance, Albert connects ethics and noetics for the first time in his commentary on *De anima* (ca. 1254). By the time he writes *Ethica*, Albert identifies contemplative happiness with the acquired intellect, the self-perfective telos of his scientific program of study. As a practical science, ethics plays an instrumental role; it is an aide to proper character and moral formation needed to undergo the long and arduous path of scientific study. As such, it seems that ethics should be studied before metaphysics. In *Ethica*, however, Albert appears to embrace a kind of radical thinking about ethics. No longer concerned with establishing ethics as a doctrina, as he was in his earlier *Super Ethica*, Albert begins his second ethical commentary by following the lead of Avicenna. Albert reinterprets Avicenna's description of ethics as the "last part of metaphysics," in order to establish the relationship between ethics and metaphysics. In this paper I argue that the defining feature between Albert's two ethical commentaries is how Albert views the relationship between ethics and metaphysics. In *Ethica*, Albert views ethics as about perfection – perfection of the human being in the acquired intellect. The science of ethics is to be studied after metaphysics.

Salle / Room 3.09

Aula 9: Radical Controversies

Ordinary Session

Chair: Alexander Fidora

Gunay Heydarli: *Religious Debates and Exchanges in the Safavid Empire: Polemical Treatises in Defense of Christianity and Islam*

In the 17th century the representatives of four missionary orders penetrated into the Safavid lands as ambassadors. Safavid Shah Abbas I gave them permission to receive military assistance against the Ottoman Empire¹. These missionaries were involved in religious debates with Shia and Armenian clergymen. These disputes led to the emerging of treatises on Christianity and Islam. During this period the ambassadors coming from European countries had presented Bibles as a gift to Shah Abbas I. The Carmelite Juan Tadeo san Eliseo started a new project to translate the Psalms and Gospels in Persian. At the same time the Zayn Al-Abidin Al-Alavi wrote the treatises on refutation of anti-islamic works. "Lavami-yi rabbaniyyah fi radd al-shubah al-Nasraniyyih (Divine Clarifications for the Confutation of Christian Doubts)" was written in response to an anti-islamic treatise from Pietro della Valle². Al-Alavi also wrote "Misqali safa" against Jeromo Xavier's treatise³. On the other side Bonaventura Malvasia and Filippo Guadagnoli were the first authors to refute Al-Alavi's work in Rome. Guadagnoli's work "Apologia" was criticized by Pietro della Valle due to lack of knowledge of Muslim sources⁴. From the sources it is clear that some friars from the Augustinian Order converted to Islam. For example, Antonio de Jesus converted to Islam and was named Ali Qulu Jadid al-Islam. The Carmelite friars sent a letter to the Pope in Rome asking them to allow them to write and translate a work that contradicts Ali Gulu Jadid's comments and to hand it over to the Safavid shah⁵. Ali Gulu Jadid al-Islam in his "Sayf al -mu' minin" criticized Guadagnoli "Apology", accusing him of ignorance of Arabic philology and spreading these misconceptions from Rome to India, Uzbekistan and the Maghreb countries as "assistants to Satan." In comparison with Guadagnoli, It should be noted that some Christian polemicists approached the Qur'an differently. They did not call it "proscribed" and "dismissive". For example, Paul of Antioch cites that verses of Surah al Ma'ida (5:48) and Surah Yunus (10:94) are evidences of divine origin of the

Qur'an. The Dominican friar, Paolo Piromalli wrote a treatise in Persian called "Risala der bayan-itikadat wa madzhab-i kalimat Allah-i isavi" and introduced it to Shah Abbas II⁶. In this research paper, we will find answers to these questions: How did religious debates contribute to intercultural development? Why were there controversial issues between Christian and Muslim scholars?

Mokdad Arfa: *Des métaphores sexuelles pour illustrer l'idée de radicalité dans la pensée islamique médiévale*

L'une des questions principales posées à cette rencontre est celle de s'interroger sur la pertinence de l'application du concept de radicalité à la philosophie médiévale. Dans un contexte islamique, nous répondons à cette question par l'affirmative, et ce, dans les deux sens du terme: celui de l'ambition de la fondation ultime qui veut en référer aux racines et aux principes, et celui de la qualification d'une démarche qui veut dégager les positions limites, s'y tenir et en assumer les conséquences. Les domaines qui sont susceptibles d'être considérés sous cet angle sont multiples et variés. En montrant l'étendue et la richesse de l'enquête éventuelle, nous nous contenterons de donner quelques exemples qui illustrent l'idée. Nous évoquerons des théories puisées dans 'Ilm al-Kalām (Théologie musulmane) par lesquelles les Mutakallimūn entendaient apporter des solutions aux problématiques classiques dans la discipline. Cela correspondait à autant de positions doctrinales prises sur les mêmes lieux théoriques. Les historiens classiques n'ont pas manqué de procéder à la classification de ces positions et de préciser leur variation en les positionnant sur une sorte d'échelle censée jauger leur teneur en radicalité. Par l'application de cette échelle, on se contentait dans la plupart des cas de mesurer la variation intra-disciplinaire sans dépasser les limites de la discipline. Des fois, on cherchait à être trans-disciplinaire, en convoquant simultanément plusieurs disciplines, dont la falsafa (philosophie), en sollicitant leur réponse à la même question et en signalant les différends entre les protagonistes. Le sérieux qu'ils affichaient dans leur quête des principes pour garantir à leur classification objectivité, rigueur et exhaustivité, s'accompagnait de notes d'humour en usant de métaphores sexuelles dans une intention dépréciative.

Görge Hasselhoff: *Ramon Martí as a Radical Thinker*

The Catalan Dominican friar Ramon Martí (ca. 1220 - ca. 1294) wrote several polemical treatises against Islam and Judaism. It is remarkable how many non-Christian sources he employed to underline his arguments. Nonetheless, his first writings, an explanation of the Apostolic Creed, a treatise on Mohammed and a treatise against Judaism, were written in Latin only. Yet, in his last and most mature work *Pugio Fidei* (Dagger of Faith, ca. 1278-94) he not only employed Latin translations of hitherto unavailable Arabic or Hebrew sources. In arguing against "all enemies of Christianity" he instead quoted Hebrew, Aramaic, and Arabic sources accompanied by Latin ad-hoc translations. Already that makes him a radical theophilosophical writer. In my talk I will present several examples from the *Pugio* to demonstrate that Martí is not only radical with regard to formal questions ("radical writer"), but also in the choice of sources and the line of argument with regard to the knowledge of God and anthropology ("radical thinker").